

Are you thinking of a smaller toilet to fit in your tiny space?

Installing a toilet that is small in a tight area is possible and could be the ideal option in your residence.

This article you'll learn about the different types of toilets for small spaces with their measurements, how they are installed benefits and drawbacks as well as the options for outfitting, prices and maintenance.

Let's start!

Types of small toilets

There are a variety of options in the kinds of toilets that are suitable for smaller spaces. One of the most sought-after choices is a corner toilet designed to fit snugly into the corner of your bathroom. This kind of toilet is typically connected to a wall-mounted tank, which takes up less space than a standard toilet. Corner toilets are available in a variety of styles and shapes, and are often the best option for bathrooms with small spaces.

Another kind of toilet is called a compact. They are usually smaller than standard size toilets and usually feature a smaller tank. They are a good choice for bathrooms that are limited on space, as they're designed to fit in tight spaces. They are also available in a variety of styles and colors, so you can find the right one to match your décor.

If you're looking for toilets that take up even less space, you may think about the wall-hung toilet. This kind of toilet is installed directly on the wall and takes up virtually nothing on the floor. Wall-hung toilets come in a range of designs and shapes, allowing you to customize your bathroom to suit your needs.

Finally, you may think about an option to use a tankless toilet. They are getting more popular because of their energy efficiency and space-saving benefits. Tankless toilets do not require tanks and are linked direct to the water, meaning they take up even less space than other types of toilets with smaller sizes.

Whichever type of small toilet you choose, you can rest assured that there is one available that will suit your needs and space. If you choose the right one you can build an attractive and functional bathroom that's perfect for your tiny space.

Measurements and Dimensions of Small Toilets

When it comes to small spaces, there are certain measurements and dimensions to consider prior to deciding on a toilet.

In general, smaller toilets are built to be able to be used in bathrooms that are limited in size. However, there are several types of small toilets that differ in shape and size.

The most popular type is the round-front designed to fit in small corners of bathrooms and typically measures around 28 inches in length. A different type is the elongated toilet that is usually 30-31 inches long and is better suited for bathrooms that are larger and have more space. There are also corner toilets, which are made to fit into the corner of the bathroom and are usually approximately 25 inches in length.

The height of small toilets is another thing to take into consideration. Standard toilets are usually around fifteen to seventeen inches high in comparison to comfort height toilets, which typically range from 17 to 19 inches high. Comfort height toilets can be beneficial for those who struggle with standing up and sitting down. Additionally, there are also toilets with a higher height, like the universal height toilet that is typically between 19 and 21 inches tall.

It is important to take into consideration the measurements and dimensions of smaller toilets prior to selecting the one you want to purchase. This will ensure that the toilet fits comfortably into the bathroom, and also that it's the right height for the user.

Installation of Small Toilets

Installing small toilets can be a complicated process particularly in small spaces. To make sure your small toilet is properly installed it is essential to know the fundamentals of how to install it.

A professional should be hired to construct the toilet since the process is precise and requires exact measurements and tools. To start, the area where the toilet will be placed must be prepared for the task. This might involve moving furniture or other items out of the way as also patching and painting the walls.

The flange then needs to be positioned on the floor where the toilet is installed. This is a crucial stage, since the flange is used to hold the toilet into position. The flange must attach to the outlet pipe prior to the toilet being set on the top. This will allow the toilet to be secured and prevents it from moving or becoming loose with time.

Once the flange is set then the toilet has to be placed carefully on top of it. This is accomplished through aligning holes on the base of the toilet to the bolts that are on the flange. After the toilet is set fixed, the bolts can be tightened to ensure the toilet is firmly secured. It is also recommended to be checked for a level surface, as an uneven toilet can cause leaks or other issues.

After the toilet has been secured in place, the connections must be put in place. The water supply line needs to be connected to the shutoff valve, while the outlet pipe must be connected to the drain. Once all of these connections have been made, the toilet is ready to be used. It is important to always verify the connections to ensure that everything is connected correctly prior to using.

The advantages of small Toilets

Small toilets come with a variety of advantages. They are less expensive and take up less space than conventional toilets. They are a good choice for small bathrooms in apartments, condos, and other small spaces. Smaller toilets require less water, making them a more economical option over the long term. The smaller size also makes them easier to clean, since you don't need to carry around a huge toilet bowl.

Small toilets can also take up less space than larger ones. This is particularly important in small bathrooms. This helps to open up the space and makes the space appear bigger. Additionally, because they are not as bulky or heavy as traditional toilets, they are easier to move around, which can be beneficial if you have to move your bathroom.

Lastly, small toilets are equally efficient as regular toilets and can be equally relaxing to utilize. Smaller toilets tend to be more efficient because they use less water. They can also be as comfy as larger toilets when you choose the correct seat and bowl layout.

In the end, smaller toilets have numerous advantages, ranging including being less expensive and making use of less space. They are a good choice for small bathrooms or apartments as well as other small spaces. They can be as comfortable and effective as normal toilets.

The disadvantages of small Toilets

Despite their many advantages smaller toilets may come with some disadvantages.

One issue is that they may not be as comfortable to use as toilets with larger sizes. Smaller bowls are a bit smaller in comparison to their larger counterparts, making it harder to locate a comfortable spot in the smaller ones. Additionally, small toilets do not offer the same quality of service as bigger ones with heated seats, as well as other amenities.

Smaller toilets can also be more costly than larger ones. They typically require more parts and work to be able to fit in smaller spaces, which can increase the price of installation. In addition, as the toilets are small, they might require regular maintenance and repairs than toilets with larger capacities.

Furthermore, some may feel that small toilets don't meet their needs and are not as comfortable as bigger ones. If you're taller person or have a bigger frame, a smaller bathroom may not be as comfortable to use. Similarly, if you have a larger family the toilet you have chosen might not be able to accommodate all of your needs.

In addition, some individuals may not be able a smaller toilet in their bathroom. If you have a small bathroom, it may not be possible to install the toilet in a smaller size without damaging the space. In addition, toilets that are small may be insufficient to fit in a bigger bathroom, making the room feel cramped.

Small bathrooms can be a great alternative for those lacking space. However, it is important to take into consideration the potential disadvantages prior to making a purchase. It is best to consider your personal needs and preferences to ensure you pick the right toilet for you.

Solutions for Outfitting a Small Toilet

When it comes to preparing a toilet with a limited room, there's several choices that will make the most of the space. First, choose a toilet that is designed to be a perfect fit for the space. A lot of toilets are smaller sizes, but don't compromise on the features. Find a toilet with a narrow projection, meaning it doesn't stick out in a way that is too close to the wall. This will save space. Also be sure to look for models with the tank built into the wall, or offer the option of installing the tank this way. This can create a more modern look and also make space for floor space.

Invest in wall-mounted storage solutions so items like cleaners and toilet papers supplies are accessible, but not in the way. Look for shelves, cabinets and trays that fit the available space. For larger items like towels, consider installing hooks on the wall to hang them from. It is also possible to hang a basket or a shelf above the toilet to store items in.

Cost Considerations for Small Toilets

Now that you've got a few ideas about what types of toilets you can pick for your small space It's time to think about the cost.

The first step is to figure out how much you are willing to pay for the toilet in your home. Prices range from low-cost to somewhat more costly. If you are on a tight budget then you might want to look at a basic one-piece bathroom, which can be purchased for only a few hundred dollars. On the other hand, if you are willing to invest more, you may wish to consider an upgraded two-piece toilet, which can be more expensive.

Also, it is important to consider the expense for installation. This can range from \$50 to \$200 dependent on the difficulty that the job. In addition, you'll want to consider the cost of any additional accessories, such as toilet seats that you may need.

In the end it is worth noting that the cost of a toilet that is small can vary greatly depending on the type you choose and any additional items you'll need.

Maintenance and care for small Toilets

Cleaning small toilets doesn't need to be difficult. with the right cleaning and maintenance, you'll be able to keep your toilet looking at its best.

Regularly cleaning your toilet is the first step. Don't forget to clean the seat, lid, and the base of the toilet, along with the inside and outside of your bowl. Use a mild detergent and an easy-to-clean cloth the bowl, then rinse it with warm water. If you want to keep the toilet sparkling and clean, you can apply a window cleaner or glass cleaner. Beware of harsh chemicals on any part of your bathroom, since it can cause damage to the material.

Another crucial aspect of maintaining your toilet is looking for leaks. If the toilet in your bathroom is leaky, it could cause major damage to the bathroom. To find leaks check for wet areas around the toilet, listen for drips, and check for water coming out from underneath the toilet. If you spot any of these indicators it is best to contact an expert plumber to address the problem.

Small toilets are also prone to clogs. To avoid this occurring, you should avoid flushing large items down your toilet, like cloths or paper towels. If your toilet becomes clogged, you can try a plunger or a toilet auger. If you're unable to unclog the toilet by yourself call an authorized plumber.

Conclusion

You've seen the types of measurements, sizes, installations, advantages, cons, and cost considerations of tiny toilets and you're now able to decide.

Whether you choose the wall-mounted model, a corner toilet or anything else, be sure to determine the size of your bathroom and ensure that it is suitable for your needs.

Making sure that your toilet is equipped with the right accessories is crucial to ensure comfort and ease of use.

Maintaining and taking care of your toilet is essential to keep your tiny toilet in the most optimal condition possible.

You can make the most of small spaces with the right small toilet.